

aquatic weed *Hydrilla verticillata*, which occurs in more permanent bodies of water such as reservoirs and canals. Several of the needle-shaped leaves are tied together by the larva to make a case. The rearing method for both aquatic caseworms was less than ideal on *Hydrilla*; only 40-50% survived to adulthood. They pupate out of water on plant vegetation.

The host range of *P. diminutalis* was three times less than *N. depunctalis* and overlapped entirely with *P. fluctuosalis*, which accepted three more plant hosts. All three caseworms shared five host plants, four of them sedges: *Fimbristylis miliacea*, *Cyperus brevifolius*, *C. difformis*, *C. rotundus*, and *Paspalum conjugatum*.

All these caseworms are similar in size and fertility (Table 2). *P. diminutalis* has four larval instars, one less than *P. fluctuosalis* and *N.*

Table 2. Life histories of *P. diminutalis* and *P. fluctuosalis* on *Hydrilla verticillata* and of *N. depunctalis* on *Oryza sativa* (IR36).^a IRR I headhouse, 1983.

Character	<i>P. diminutalis</i>	<i>P. fluctuosalis</i>	<i>N. depunctalis</i>
Fertility (no. eggs/female) ^b	130	125	117
Egg incubation period (d)	5.5	4.5	4.5
Larval developmental period (d)			
First stadium	2.5	3.0	3.5
Second stadium	3.3	3.9	3.8
Third stadium	3.3	4.5	4.1
Fourth stadium	4.0	4.5	4.5
Fifth stadium	— ^c	5.3	5.8
Pupal period (d)	6.9	9.6	7.9
Male longevity (d)	4.2	3.1	3.0
Female longevity (d)	4.3	3.9	5.0
Sex ratio (male:female)	1:1.5	1:1.2	1:1
Developmental period from egg to adult ^d (d)	29.8	39.2	39.1

^aAv of 20 replications except when indicated otherwise. ^bAv of 5 pairs. ^cNo fifth stadium. ^dFemale.

depunctalis; matures about 10 d earlier than the 2; and has a longer egg incubation period. The sex ratio favored the development of females in *P. diminutalis* and *P. fluctuosalis*,

probably because of the lack of a better rearing method. The present rearing method seemed to favor larger individuals, which were mostly females. ♂

Chromosomes of the primary spermatocytes of *Nephotettix nigropictus* (Stål)

R. C. Saxena, International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology (ICIPE), Kenya, and International Rice Research Institute (IRRI); and A. A. Barrion, Institute of Biological Sciences, University of the Philippines at Los Baños

The testicular primary spermatocytes of newly emerged green leafhopper *N. nigropictus* contained first meiotic holocentric chromosomes. At diakinesis (Fig. 1a), the genomic complement consisted of 7 bivalent autosomes plus a univalent X-chromosome. Therefore, the diploid chromosome number of male *N. nigropictus* is $2n = 15 (7II_A + XO)$.

The prospective spermatozoa are of 2 types: $n = 8 (7I_A + X)$ and $n = 7 (7I_A + 0)$. During metaphase I (Fig. 1b), the heterochromatic X-body can be seen isolated from autosomes at the equatorial plate.

Pachytene analysis showed that the whole genome of males consisted of eight linkage groups (Fig. 2). The longest autosome was almost double

1. Chromosomes of male *N. nigropictus* at a) diakinesis showing $2n = 15$, b) metaphase I. Spontaneous aberration may result in c) an agmatoploid cell with $2n = 19 (9II + X)$. IRR I, 1985-86. The sex chromosome is indicated by an arrow. Magnification 1500X (oil immersion).

the shortest. The relative mean lengths of chromosomes ranged from 0.062 to 0.165. The sex chromosome measured 0.062 and the autosome with the nucleolar organizing region (NOR) 0.155.

The chromosomes condensed maximally during premetaphase into dumbbells of bivalents measuring 3.9μ , 3.3μ (NOR), 2.7μ , 2.5μ , 2.4μ , 2.1μ , 2.0μ , and 1.6μ (X). Their

2. Camera lucida drawing of pachytene chromosomes of *N. nigropictus* and their idiogram. IRR I, 1985-86. The sex chromosome is indicated by an arrow. Magnification 1250X (oil immersion).

corresponding chromosome volumes were $0.025 \mu^3$, $0.015 \mu^3$, $0.009 \mu^3$, $0.007 \mu^3$, $0.007 \mu^3$, $0.004 \mu^3$, $0.003 \mu^3$, and $0.001 \mu^3$.

The mean meiotic index approximated 0.61, the mean number of dividing spermatocytes was 227, the number of nondividing cells was 147.

Of 100 cells at diakinesis, 24% contain a reduced number of bivalents and 5% possessed an increased number of chromosomes (Fig. 1c). ♂